

How does experience influence usability expectations in human-robot interaction? Results of a worker evaluation in an industrial setting*

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Abstract— This paper presents results of a worker evaluation in three industrial use cases, focusing on the assessment of expected usability aspects within human-robot interaction and their relation to the level of experience. 27 workers from three different European companies were asked about their expectations of working with an interactive robotic system, using statements about the dialogue principles based on ISO standard 9241-110:2019. The results show a significant difference between the two groups of experienced and inexperienced workers for multiple principles. Learnability and Controllability are rated less important with more experience while Suitability for the task and Individualization grow in importance with the level of experience. Overall, the results show that it is most important for the users that the functionalities of the system meet their expectations. Limitations regarding sample size and allocation are discussed. Nevertheless, the presented results and interpretations underline the importance of considering workers' expectations during the technology development process

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the introduction of different kinds of robotic systems has increased significantly in a wide range of industries and work areas [1]. Especially within the manufacturing industry, numerous areas of application can be found; the automotive sector in particular is becoming increasingly automated and sophisticated [2, 3]. However, this does not mean that the importance of humans has diminished - human labour is still a decisive production factor [4]. Therefore, the aim of increasing efficiency and productivity to improve a company's competitiveness is not only achieved by fully automated manufacturing: The automation of individual tasks through robotic systems can contribute to this objective by improving the ergonomics of a workplace and, more broadly, improve occupational health and safety [5]. As a result, humans and robots are working together more frequent and more closely [6]. In this regard, the interaction between humans and robots, and especially its quality, is becoming increasingly important [7]. To capitalise on the desired opportunities by ensuring a certain degree of interaction quality, the development and implementation of interactive robotic systems should be based human-centred rather than technology-driven. One fundamental aspect that contributes to the overall interaction quality is the usability of the system [3]. This technology-related facet is, according to the ISO 9241, defined as “*the extent to which a product can be used by*

specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction in a specified context of use” [8].

Another major aspect that can be used to evaluate and describe the quality of human-robot interaction is the concept of technology acceptance: The user's acceptance of the robotic system can be negatively affected by a low usability, especially in terms of perceived usefulness and ease of use [9]. However, acceptance as a human-related facet is not only determined by the functionality of a robot, it is also influenced by the user's expectations of interacting with the specific system, as well as their experience with a particular kind of technology. The worker's attitude and expectations towards a newly introduced technology can also make a significant contribution to the success of its implementation and acceptance, in order to prevent misuse, disuse or abuse of the system [10].

Against this background, when designing and implementing new robotic systems in the context of work, two aspects need to be taken into account, which should ideally be closely related: an emphasis on usability (design) principles and the consideration of the end-user perspective right from the beginning of the (technology) development process. In order to implement this approach right from the beginning, the research project SOPHIA (“Socio-Physical Interaction Skills for Cooperative Human-Robot Systems in Agile Production”), funded by the European Commission [11], chose an iterative evaluation process. The underlying structure for this can be found in the HTO framework. This concept, derived from the field of human factors and ergonomics, is widely used in the design and implementation of new technologies or systems. In particular, it emphasises a human-centred perspective by considering the importance of the interaction between the three main interdependent subsystems - Human (H), Technology (T), and Organisation (O) - in any socio-technical system [12]. By focusing on the interaction between these three subsystems, instead of considering each independently, the HTO framework can shine a light on ongoing and changing processes in a dynamic system, which result from the relationship between the sub-systems. Applying the HTO framework can therefore provide guidance on how a system can be designed or retrofitted to better support workers health, as well as both individual and systems performance [12].

This approach contributes significantly to the project's objective of developing work systems with humans and robotic components to increase the productivity and flexibility

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of manual manufacturing and to improve its physical and cognitive ergonomics. Concerning usability aspects, the project has carried out both large-scale online surveys and the evaluation of specific pilot use cases in order to allow a comprehensive involvement of (potential) end-users from different (industrial) sectors as well as workers associated with manufacturing use cases from the beginning of the project activities.

This paper reports on three industrial use cases, in which workers evaluated robotic systems, with a focus on their expectations towards system usability. The evaluation was conducted at the beginning of the project to identify requirements and needs that could be incorporated into the project as it progressed. In accordance with the HTO Concept, it presents the results regarding the dialogue principles, according to ISO standard 9241-110:2019 [9], as technology related aspect and the connection to prior experience with robots as human-related facet. In particular the aim was to find out whether and how familiarity with robotic systems affects expectations of these principles, and what conclusions can be drawn for the design and implementation of robotic systems in operational practice in general and within the project. To achieve this, the evaluation focused on workers who were highly involved in the chosen use cases, i.e. who have specific experience of the particular workstation and the (manual) working task which can be seen as an organisational component.

In the following sections, we give an introduction to usability design within human-robot interaction (HRI), present the different use cases and their specifications are described, as well as the procedure of the study, followed by the description of the sample and the statistical analysis. The results are then presented, interpreted and discussed.

A. Usability design within HRI: Dialogue principles

A system's usability is one fundamental aspect that contributes to the acceptance of the robotic system as well as the overall quality of interaction [3]. For example, if a technology, and how to interact with it, is perceived as too complex, those working with it may feel overwhelmed by it use. This can have a negative impact on the working situation, particularly with regard to performance as well as acceptance of and trust in the system. These concepts are crucial not only to user behavior but also to the potential misuse and disuse of the system, directly impacting the efficiency and effectiveness of (workers) productivity [13]. The ISO standard 9241-110:2019 provides general interaction principles for the ergonomic design of interactive systems. These seven design facets can guide the development and evaluation of user interfaces and are highly relevant to its overall usability. They have also been shown as a suitable tool for user evaluation of robotic systems [14] as well as to be important and useful for system interaction design in the context of Industry 4.0 [15]. The new level of automation in robotics that is entering the workplace right now brings a new quality of interaction that could be assessed and improved by applying these principles early in the development process. A detailed description of dialogue principle is shown in Table I.

The advantage of these principles is that they are applicable to each use case and its specific needs, but also allow

generalised design recommendations for further development (steps) to be derived. Another variable that was assessed in each use case is the level of experience workers had with the given technology. According to the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), it moderates performance expectancy, effort expectancy and social influence and thus influences the user's behavioural intention to use a technology [9].

TABLE I. DIALOGUE PRINCIPLES FOLLOWING ISO STANDARD 9241-110:2019

Dialogue Principle	Description
Suitability for the task	The user-system interactions are based on the task characteristics and support the completion of the task.
Self-descriptiveness	The interactive system presents appropriate information to make its capabilities and use immediately obvious to the user without unnecessary user-system interactions.
Controllability	The system allows the user to maintain control of the user interface and the interactions, including the speed and sequence and individualization of the user-system interaction.
Conformity to user expectations	The system's behaviour is predictable based on the context of use and commonly accepted conventions in this context.
Error tolerance	The interactive system assists the user in avoiding errors and in case of identifiable errors treats them tolerantly and assists the user when recovering from errors.
Suitability for individualization	The possibility of adapting the robot to the workers' needs and abilities.
Learnability	The system supports discovery of its capabilities and how to use it minimizes the need for learning and provides support when learning is needed.

II. METHODOLOGY

This part describes the different use cases and their specifications with regard to the respective tasks and the company context in which they are embedded. The evaluation procedure and the specifications for each use case are described as well as the statistical analysis of the data.

A. Use-case descriptions

Three different companies are involved in the SOPHIA project. These companies are all in the manufacturing sector, but differ in size, core business and country of origin: company 1 is a large company from Slovenia, company 2 is a small company based in the Netherlands and the third company is the largest in Germany. This allows the project to consider different manufacturing scenarios across different European countries. The specific use case scenario for each company was selected following a detailed workplace assessment to identify a suitable task that could be facilitated by a robotic system. The selected pilot use cases had in common that they involved repetitive tasks that had recently been performed manually. For company 1, the use case considered was the unloading of steel laminates after an annealing line. For company 2, the manufacturing process of gear cutting was selected, including the (un)fixing, transport and cleaning of the relevant products. For company 3, it was the manufacturing

process of applying the rubber seal to a car body. In all cases, the introduction of a robotic system aims to improve the physical ergonomics of the worker, as well as the efficiency of the individual and the overall productivity of the company, without negatively affecting aspects of cognitive ergonomics.

B. Evaluation procedure

The scientific analysis was focused on the workers' expectations regarding aspects associated with the system's usability. Beforehand an ethics approval was obtained and a data privacy statement was conducted and approved by the organisations' data privacy officer. The data was collected in autumn 2020. As on-site visits were not possible due to the COVID-19 situation, video calls were used, with workers participating individually or in small groups. For company 1 and 2, the provision of the questionnaire-based survey was nearly the same. For company 2, seven workers and 13 workers from company 1 participated in the evaluation survey. For the provision of the survey, two different video calls each were set up, where the workers participated in small groups of four and three or six persons. In addition to the scientists who conducted the research, the responsible project leader from the company joined the meetings for coordinating and supporting the survey process. The participants therefore had the opportunity to ask any kind of questions during the whole process. Each round of the survey took about one to one and a half hours. The process started with a presentation aiming at introducing the project, the involved partners and the procedure of the survey. For company 1, the project leader on site translated this presentation in Slovene simultaneously. Before the participants were asked to give their informed consent, the central points of the participation modalities, data privacy issues and voluntariness of the participation were explained. After presenting the necessary information and answering all remaining questions, the workers signed the informed consent as well as the data privacy statement. As the aim of the study was to collect data on expectations even before the actual robot had been developed, the workers were asked to imagine themselves working together with a robot that could do various tasks to support their daily work. To give the workers a better idea of the intended scenario, a picture of the addressed workstation and a picture of the chosen basis platform, as an anchor example for the collaborative robots, was shown. For company 2, an English version of the questionnaire was used to avoid information loss due to translation. The responsible project partner was around to help with potential language misunderstandings. For company 1, the responsible project manager translated the questionnaire into Slovenian. In addition, all necessary documents as well as the introductory presentation for the employees were translated to ensure comprehensive information.

For company 3, the process had to be adapted due to the current circumstances because the workers were already experienced in working with the robotic system since it was introduced some weeks prior. Therefore, the objective was to gather expectations of robotic systems from a more general point of view: The participants were asked to picture that the functionality of a different robotic system would exceed the level of the current system. In this case, seven workers participated in one-by-one video calls on different days over a period of about two weeks. Again, a short presentation including all necessary information was prepared and

presented to each participant. During the whole process, again, the conducting scientist and one responsible from the company were available for questions. For the most part, already existing and established German versions of the concepts addressed were used. In all cases, the workers filled in paper pencil versions of the survey, which were returned via mail to the responsible scientists for the analysis.

C. Sample and Measures

As the aim of the study was to involve only workers who were used to working regularly at the use case workstations, the number of potential participants was limited to that specific target group. For data privacy reasons, age was not recorded, as identification would have been possible due to the size of the sample. The participants' experience of working with robotic systems and their familiarity with robots was assessed by the statements: "I have often seen robots in real life" and "I have a lot of experience working with robots" on a 5 point scale from 1 "strongly disagree" to 5 "strongly agree" and the option to choose "no idea". As a base for the assessment of the expected usability, a short and adapted version of the IsoMetrics was used [16]. Further details on this can be found in Heinold et al. [17]. This consists of 7 items, of which each refers to one of the dialogue principles from the ISO 9241. The same scale from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree" with the option for "no idea" was used.

D. Statistical Analysis

For the data analysis, SPSS Statistics Version 29 was used. On average, the participating workers were rather familiar with robots ($M = 3.6$, $SD = 1.38$) but had only partly experience working with robots ($M = 2.4$, $SD = 1.0$). However, the group was rather heterogeneous. Less so, when dividing the dataset by the three involved companies it was visible that one had much less contact with robots than the other two. It became clear that the group included both, very experienced workers as well as complete novices. For further analysis, it was therefore aimed at dividing the dataset into experienced and inexperienced participants. To create this value for prior experience the two mentioned statements for familiarity and working experience were cumulated. A participant was considered experienced if their score was above 3.0 and inexperienced if they scored 3.0 and below. The means and standard deviations were calculated for the whole sample as well as for the group of experienced and inexperienced workers separately.

Using a linear regression model, it was then tested, if the expected system's usability could be predicted by prior experience. Consequently, a linear regression model was chosen. Consequently, the overall expected usability was calculated out of the answers on the seven dialogue principles by adding their values and dividing the result by seven. In order to get insights about which aspect of the interaction with a robotic system was of most interest to the participants, the mean values of each principle was calculated. From this, it was possible to test for the contribution of prior experience on all dialogue principles separately, using unpaired t-tests.

III. RESULTS

In total, 27 workers participated in the survey. All of them were male and directly connected to the identified use cases in the pilot area. The companies differed in the average reported level of familiarity and work experience with robots (Table II).

TABLE II. MEAN VALUES AND STANDARD DEVIATIONS OF THE LEVEL OF FAMILIARITY AND WORK EXPERIENCE WITH ROBOTS

Company	Familiarity		Work experience	
	M / SD	M / SD	M / SD	M / SD
C1	2.92	1.56	1.91	1.13
C2	4.29	0.49	3.0	0.82
C3	4.29	1.11	2.7	0.76

While company 2 and company 3 only had one inexperienced participant out of 7, company one had 8 out of 10, summing up to fourteen experienced and 10 inexperienced participants. The company with the most inexperienced participants (C1) had the least expectations regarding the system's usability ($M = 3.05, SD = 1.0$). Both other companies, although the level of experience was very similar, differed in their expectations regarding usability (C2: $M = 3.9, SD = 0.4$; C3: $M = 3.4, SD = 0.58$).

There were some differences in the mean rating of all statements. Less experienced participants had lower expectations ($M = 2.6, SD = 0.83$) than experienced participants ($M = 3.7, SD = 0.49$). The results for each dialogue principle for experienced and inexperienced participants as well as for the whole sample are shown in Table III.

TABLE III. MEAN VALUES AND STANDARD DEVIATIONS FOR DIALOGUE PRINCIPLES

Principle	Whole sample		Inexperienced		Experienced	
	M / SD	M / SD	M / SD	M / SD	M / SD	M / SD
Suitability for the task	3.52	1.22	2.6	1.35	4.07	0.73
Learnability	3.44	0.80	2.9	0.88	3.71	0.61
Self-descriptiveness	3.12	0.95	2.33	0.87	3.57	0.76
Controllability	3.4	1.12	2.78	1.20	3.85	0.56
Conformity to user expectations	3.74	0.90	3.1	0.99	4.00	0.56
Error tolerance	3.11	1.15	2.4	0.97	3.43	1.09
Suitability for individualization	3.3	1.35	2.2	1.14	3.86	1.03

The overall lowest ranked statement was "Small errors of workers will not lead to serious consequences" ($M = 3.1, SD = 1.15$) used for *Error tolerance* and the highest mean rating was given to the statement "I will always know what every function of the robot can be used for" ($M = 3.74, SD = 0.90$) used for *Conformity to user expectations*. Again, the data was divided in inexperienced and experienced participants. The latter rated *Error tolerance* the lowest ($M = 3.43, SD = 1.09$) while the former least expected the *Suitability for individualization* (M

$= 2.2, SD = 1.1$). For inexperienced participants, the most expected principle was the *Conformity with user's expectations* ($M = 3.1, SD = 0.99$) while those with more experience gave most relevance to the *Suitability for the task* ($M = 4.07, SD = 0.73$). *Conformity to user expectations* a rated quite high in both groups, while *Error tolerance* and *Self-descriptiveness* are rated less important. *Self-descriptiveness* is also the only principle that has the same ranking position in both groups. A raking list based on mean values of all principles for both groups is shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV. RANKING LIST OF DIALOGUE PRINCIPLES

Rank	Inexperienced	Experienced
Most important	Conformity to user expectations	Suitability for the task
2	Learnability	Conformity to user expectations
3	Controllability	Suitability for individualization
4	Suitability for the task	Controllability
5	Error tolerance	Learnability
6	Self-descriptiveness	Self-descriptiveness
Least important	Suitability for individualization	Error tolerance

In order to perform unpaired t-test to test for statistically significant group differences, 5 data sets were excluded from the analysis due to missing data. The result of the unpaired t-test showed that there is a statistically significant difference between the ratings of all inexperienced and experienced workers for all seven principles. For *Suitability for the task* ($t(22) = 3.45, p < 0.001$), *Self-descriptiveness* ($t(21) = 3.62, p < 0.001$) and *Suitability for individualization* ($t(22) = 3.731, p < 0.001$) the result are even highly significant. .

TABLE V. T-TEST RESULTS

	F	Sig.	T (df)	p
Suitability for the task	7.809	0.011	3.451 (22)	0.001**
Learnability	1.929	0.179	2.690 (22)	0.007*
Self-descriptiveness	0.035	0.854	3.624 (21)	<0.001**
Controllability	7.085	0.015	2.822 (20)	0.005*
Conformity to user expectations	3.682	0.068	2.839 (22)	0.005*
Error tolerance	0.515	0.480	2.387 (22)	0.013*
Suitability for individualization	0.153	0.699	3.731 (22)	<0.001**

IV. DISCUSSION AND LIMITATIONS

When looking at experienced workers, the expectations regarding all seven dialog principles and therefore the overall system usability is considerably statistically higher compared to the inexperienced ones (for a better overview of the results for both groups see Fig. 1). This indicates that usability ratings can be influenced by prior experience and emphasizes the

Figure 1: Mean values for dialogue principles from inexperienced and experienced workers; ** significant difference in unpaired t-test

consideration of the level of experience within HRI. However, in this case, when interpreting the results, the constitution of the sample should be considered: Most of the inexperienced participants are employed by the same company. Therefore, it should be assumed that these results are probably not only influenced by prior experience. Also organizational, and in this case, culturally specific aspects can also influence the expectations regarding the systems' usability. This result and the associated circumstances described are in line and underline the importance of the HTO framework: The sub-system human is characterise, among others aspects, as a member of social groups, like a member of a company, and cultures. It is also be seen as a "a *psychic subject with a unique history*" [13] which can also include individual experiences and expectations. A further development of this concept promotes the meaningfulness of the working task which interconnected all three sub-systems [13]. This importance is also evident in the results through high ratings for *Suitability for the task* across the entire sample and especially among experienced employees. Conversely, workers with less experience attach less importance to this principle. Another reason for this may be that workers have had negative experiences in this respect. Again, this underlines the importance of this principle, as it is often seen as a predictable result, but may find little application in (operational) practice. This may again be the result of a technology-driven development or implementation process.

Moreover, the higher ratings by experienced participants might imply that prior experience leads to higher expectations respectively requirements regarding a newly introduced robotic system compared to inexperienced workers. In combination with the rating of *Conformity of user expectations*, which is the highest rated principle over the whole sample and only slightly lower than the highest rated principle of *Suitability for the task* in the group of experienced

workers, this gives a high emphasize on the need of incorporating the end users' perspective. To ensure that the functionalities and design specifications are in line with user expectations, it is necessary to identify these for the specific target group in the addressed use case setting.

For three principles out of seven, the statistical difference is highly significant. These results can be interpreted to mean that workers with higher experience hold *Self-descriptiveness*, *Suitability for individualization* and for *Suitability for the task* to a higher importance than inexperienced workers. These principles should be carefully considered to enable a long-term and sustainable robot use. This implies that workers' expectations or requirements of the importance of a robotic system's functionalities change overtime. For both operational practice and technology development, this suggests the need for iterative evaluation to ensure optimal quality of human-robot interaction.

For experienced workers, *Learnability* and *Controllability* are less important than for inexperienced workers who place the second and third highest value on these principles. This is not surprising because a deficiency of these functionalities can probably be compensated by experience. For the whole sample, the lowest rated principle is *Error tolerance*. Since the results show that the system is not expected to work perfectly, it is more advisable to present a system to the workers at an early stage in order to involve them, rather than waiting for it to mature. The benefits in terms of design and perception of usability will outweigh any (functional) shortcomings and, over time, a better match with expectations can be achieved.

In addition to the limitations mentioned concerning sample allocation, there are also limitations in relation to targeting task-related participants from pilot use case areas. On the one hand, this means that the number of potential participants is limited. On the other hand, as the aim was also to find the best

fit between technology and task, the participants had similar starting situations but ended up evaluating different robotic systems. Besides, the underlying standard and the dialogue principles contained therein were revised after the study was conducted. Further research in this area is therefore needed. Ideally, a dedicated analysis of all parameters should be carried out, as human, technology and organisation may influence the expectations and evaluation of each dialogue principle.

Furthermore, the underlying ISO standard 9241-110:2019, has recently undergone structural and content changes. In 2020, the dialogue principles were renamed to interaction principles and a new one, *User engagement*, was added. The data collection process of the here presented research was finalised before the updated norm was published. Future research in this area should use the updated norm as a base.

V. CONCLUSION

The presented results show that workers with a higher level of experience have different expectations towards a systems usability than inexperienced ones regarding usability aspects of robotic systems. For operational practice, the significant differences between the two groups suggests that previous experience should always be taken into account when designing interactive robotic systems. This should not only be done on a general level but also for each specific target group or even individual person, which means that the employees need to be involved in the development process.

The benefits of incorporating (end) users from an early stage to create interactive robotic systems are moreover twofold: as shown, different target groups or even persons can have various expectations and therewith individual and specific requirements to the functionality of the robotic system. Special attention should be given to the *Suitability for the task*, as it is an important part of the socio-technical system and beneficial for long term use behaviour. Additionally, users might accept the robot and associated changes better when involving them in the development process. This, in turn, can have a direct impact on the usage behaviour and therefore effects the realisation of desired (economical) benefits.

Even though some limitations regarding the sample size and allocation should be considered, the presented results and interpretations underline the importance of a detailed consideration of the target group and the specific environmental factors of the working task and organization following the HTO framework.

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